

Grain quality

Effect of temperature regime on grain chalkiness in rice

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Grain quality determines the market price of rice. High-yielding varieties with low grain quality are not well accepted by farmers and consumers.

Chalkiness is an important grain quality characteristic because it causes broken grains and nonuniformity of the physical appearance of grains. Chalkiness varies even in the same variety and location. It may be possible that the factors affecting the accumulation of photosynthate during spikelet filling also affect the compactness of starch granules, causing chalkiness.

Temperature affects almost all processes in plants, and chalkiness is probably

not an exception. We studied the effect of temperature regime on chalkiness in rice grains.

Seeds of three cultivars (LMN111, PG56, and HTA60) were sown in Aug 1992 in pots with puddled Maahas clay soil mixed with 3 g of ammonium sulfate. Three seeds were sown per pot but only one plant per pot was left to grow. One month after emergence, the plants were subjected to a 10-h photoperiod to induce flowering. At flowering, they were placed in temperature-controlled growth chambers, with natural light and 80% relative humidity until maturity. The day/night temperature regimes used were: 22/15, 25/15, 30/20, and 35/20 °C. After harvest, rice grains were dehulled and scored for chalkiness using the procedure of the Rice Grain Quality Laboratory, Rice Research Institute, Thailand: 0 = no chalkiness, 1 = less than 10% chalky area, 2 = 10-20%, 3 = 20-50%, 4 = 50-75%, and 5 = above 75%.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications.

The high temperature regime (35/20 °C) had the most adverse effect on percentage of filled spikelets in all cultivars tested. At low temperatures (22/15 °C), HTA60 was the least sensitive while LMN111 and PG56 had comparable high sensitivity. The 30/20 °C temperature regime resulted in a higher percentage of filled spikelets for the three cultivars tested; HTA60 was the least sensitive to temperature regime (Fig. 1).

Optimum temperatures for low chalkiness were 25/15 °C and 30/20 °C (Fig. 2). Low temperature (22/15 °C) increased chalkiness but not as serious as did high temperature (35/20 °C), although low temperature affected panicle exertion and percentage of fertile spikelets. Despite low number of spikelets to fill, high temperature resulted in poor spikelet filling, although leaves were still green.

Temperature affected chalkiness. Under field conditions, temperature cannot be controlled, so the best way to reduce chalkiness is to select cultivars that are less sensitive to temperature, such as PG56. ■

Scented rice in Jiangxi Province, China

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Gan-xian-da-he-zi, Gi-shui-xiang-nu, Gi-an-xiang-he-zi, and Long-nan-xiang-he are traditional local scented rice cultivars in Jiangxi Province. All three of these are unsuitable for cultivation because of their tall stature, low yield potential, and poor grain appearance, which does not meet the demands of the modern rice market.

We started to work on breeding new scented rices in 1985. Many aromatic rices, including IR841, Basmati 370, and Khao Dawk Mali 105, were selected for use in the crossing program. We followed the objective of breeding semidwarf, high quality rice with slender grain and at least 5% higher yield than

Shuang-zhu-zhan, a high quality rice variety planted widely in southern China.

Two semidwarf indica scented rice varieties were produced. Gan-wan-xian 22 was released for commercial production in Mar 1994 by the Seed Board of Jiangxi Province. It is the first modern scented variety in Jiangxi Province.

Gan-wan-xian 22 was derived from the cross IR841/84-06, a strain from the cross of IR24/Gui-chao. The selected strain SR4044 has aromatic grain, good grain appearance, intermediate amylose content (AC) and gelatinization temperature (GC), soft gel consistency (GC), and promising agronomic characteristics (see table). It yielded 5.3 t/ha in regional trials for the late rice crop in the double-cropped system in 1992-93 and was not significantly different from the high-yielding check M112. It yielded 15% more than Shuang-zhu-zhan. Its average yield was 4.5-6.8 t/ha. In Oct 1992, Jiangxi-xiang-si-miao rice, a commercial product of Gan-wan-xian 22, won a bronze prize at the First China Agriculture Exposition.

SR5041, another preferred scented rice variety was also put into production. It is from the cross of IR841/Zao-xiang 17, has a heavy fragrance, low AC value, low GT, and soft GC (see table). The average yield was about 4.1 t/ha, which

Quality characteristics of Gan-wan-xian 22, SR5041, and Shuang-zhu-zhan.^a

Characteristic	Gan-wan-xian 22	SR5041	Shuang-zhu-zhan
Milling quality			
Brown rice (%)	79.6	80.1	76.4
Milled rice recovery (%)	70.1	70.5	71.1
Head rice (%)	60.1	61.5	67.8
Grain appearance			
1,000-grain whole			
Milled rice weight (g)	18.4	20.2	12.1
Kernel length (mm)	6.9	7.2	5.8
L-W ratio	3.3	3.4	2.9
Chalky kernels (%)	14.0	9.0	9.0
Area with chalkiness (%)	1.9	1.5	1.3
Chemical characteristics			
AC value (%)	20.1	16.1	26.6
Alkali spreading value	4.1	7.0	6.0
GC value (mm)	83.0	66.0	29.0
Protein content of milled rice (%)	6.5	7.1	6.7
Eating quality			
Cooked rice elongation	1.6	1.7	1.2
Aroma	Medium	Strong	None
Taste	Good	Very good	Good

^aSamples were from late rice crop in the double-cropped system, late 1992.

was 10% more than that of Shuang-zhu-zhan.

Gan-wan-xian 22 has good resistance to blast and brown planthopper. It was cultivated as a late rice variety in Jiangxi Province in 1993 on about 10,000 ha.

SR5041, also a late rice, has a growth duration that is 10 d shorter than that of Gan-wan-xian 22, which is similar to that of Shuang-zhu-zhan. Both scented rices are very popular in the local markets and are being exported to Southeast Asia. ■

Stability of rice grain quality under different fertilizer levels

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We conducted this experiment to study how the levels of fertilizer affect the stability of rice grain quality. Six varieties were grown in the 1993 wet season in a stability model where three N levels (0, 40, and 80 kg/ha), two P levels (0 and 40 kg/ha), and two K

levels (0 and 30 kg/ha) were combined into 12 fertilizer levels. Rice was dehulled using a Satake rice husking machine (model THU-35A) and McGill polisher no. 3.

The percentages of brown rice, white rice, and broken rice in all varieties were unstable under different fertilizer levels, with S^2_{di} significant from zero (Table 1). The responses of milling quality to fertilizer levels did not follow the linear model, suggesting that milling quality was affected by many other factors in addition to fertilizer levels.

Table 1. Stability parameters for milling quality of some varieties.

Variety	Brown rice(%)			White rice (%)			Broken rice (%)		
	\bar{X}	bi	S^2_{di}	\bar{X}	bi	S^2_{di}	\bar{X}	bi	S^2_{di}
OM987-1	77.8	0.77	0.65	68.2	0.73	2.09	36.1	0.27	35.34
IR58082	76.8	3.63	5.19	66.8	2.36	9.46	33.8	0.17	16.10
MTL 105	78.5	-0.04	0.14	70.0	0.28	0.56	21.5	2.92	54.14
OM269	78.8	0.49	5.49	69.6	0.69	5.68	30.4	1.59	66.80
IR53964-39	77.9	0.91	0.76	68.3	0.87	2.69	23.3	1.43	40.67
IR29723	78.3	0.21	0.35	68.8	1.16	2.09	23.0	0.17	30.63

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